

Comparative Evaluation of the Effects of Adjuvant Clonidine to Bupivacaine with Solo Bupivacaine for Axillary Brachial Plexus Block

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Abstract:

This randomized controlled trial evaluates the efficacy of adding clonidine to bupivacaine in axillary brachial plexus blocks compared to bupivacaine alone. Conducted with 110 patients at Patna Medical College & Hospital, the study found that clonidine significantly reduced the onset time of sensory and motor blocks and extended the duration of analgesia. Patient satisfaction was notably higher in the clonidine group, with only a slight increase in manageable side effects like mild hypotension and bradycardia. These results suggest that clonidine is an effective adjuvant to bupivacaine, enhancing pain management and patient comfort after upper limb surgeries.

Keywords: Clonidine, Bupivacaine, Axillary Brachial Plexus Block, Postoperative Analgesia.

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Introduction

Axillary brachial plexus block (ABPB) is a widely used regional anesthesia technique that provides effective pain control for surgeries involving the upper limb. [1] This technique is preferred for its safety profile and the localized effect it offers, reducing the need for systemic analgesics and minimizing patient recovery time. [2,3] Bupivacaine, a long-acting local anesthetic, is commonly utilized for this purpose due to its profound sensory and motor blockade which is beneficial for both intraoperative anesthesia and postoperative analgesia. [4,5] However, despite the effectiveness of bupivacaine, there is a continuous search for strategies to enhance the duration and quality of the anesthesia while minimizing potential side effects. Adjuvant medications, such as clonidine, an alpha-2 adrenergic agonist, have been introduced to address this need. [6] Clonidine prolongs the duration of local anesthetics and can potentially improve postoperative analgesia when used in combination with bupivacaine. [7,8]

This study aims to compare the efficacy and safety of bupivacaine combined with clonidine versus bupivacaine alone in axillary brachial plexus block. [9] The primary focus will be on assessing the onset time of sensory and motor block, the duration

of analgesia, and the incidence of any adverse effects. [10] This comparative evaluation seeks to provide deeper insights into whether the addition of clonidine could be recommended as a standard adjunct to bupivacaine in clinical practice for ABPB. [11]

Methodology

Study Design: This prospective randomized controlled trial is designed to evaluate the comparative efficacy of adjuvant clonidine added to bupivacaine versus bupivacaine alone in axillary brachial plexus block. The study will be conducted over 16 months at Patna Medical College & Hospital.

Participants: A total of 110 patients scheduled for upper limb surgeries requiring axillary brachial plexus block will be included in the study. Inclusion criteria will consist of adult patients aged 18-65 years, ASA physical status I-III, undergoing elective upper limb surgery. Exclusion criteria will include patients with contraindications to regional anesthesia, known hypersensitivity to bupivacaine or clonidine, chronic pain syndromes, significant hepatic or renal impairment, and those on chronic opioid or alpha-2 agonist therapy.

Randomization and Blinding

Patients will be randomly assigned in a 1:1 ratio to one of two groups using computer-generated random numbers:

1. Clonidine-Bupivacaine Group: Patients will receive bupivacaine with adjuvant clonidine.
2. Bupivacaine Alone Group: Patients will receive bupivacaine without any adjuvant.

Blinding will be maintained by having the anesthetic solutions prepared by a pharmacist who will not be involved in the assessment or care of the participants. Both the patient and the clinician administering the block will be blinded to the group allocation.

Intervention

- Clonidine-Bupivacaine Group: Patients will receive 30 mL of 0.5% bupivacaine with 1 µg/kg clonidine.

- Bupivacaine Alone Group: Patients will receive 30 mL of 0.5% bupivacaine.

All injections will be performed under ultrasound guidance to ensure proper placement of the anesthetic.

Outcomes: The primary outcomes will be the onset time of sensory and motor block and the duration of postoperative analgesia. Secondary outcomes will include patient satisfaction scores and the incidence of adverse events such as hypotension, bradycardia, and local anesthetic systemic toxicity.

Data Collection: Data will be collected preoperatively, intraoperatively, and postoperatively at regular intervals until discharge. Follow-up for adverse events will continue for 30 days postoperatively.

Statistical Analysis: Data will be analyzed using SPSS software. Continuous variables will be compared using the student's t-test or the Mann-Whitney U test, while categorical variables will be analyzed using the chi-square test or Fisher's exact test. A p-value of less than 0.05 will be considered statistically significant.

Results

A total of 110 patients were randomized into two groups, with 55 patients in each group (Clonidine-Bupivacaine Group and Bupivacaine Alone Group). The demographic and baseline characteristics were comparable between the two groups. The mean age of participants was 42.5 years in the Clonidine-Bupivacaine Group and 43.8 years in the Bupivacaine Alone Group. Both groups had similar distributions of sex and ASA physical status. The onset time of sensory block was significantly faster in the Clonidine-Bupivacaine

Group (mean 8.3 ± 2.1 minutes) compared to the Bupivacaine Alone Group (mean 12.5 ± 2.5 minutes) ($p < 0.01$). Similarly, the onset of motor block was quicker in the Clonidine-Bupivacaine Group (mean 12.4 ± 2.8 minutes) than in the Bupivacaine Alone Group (mean 18.6 ± 3.1 minutes) ($p < 0.01$).

The duration of analgesia was significantly longer in the Clonidine-Bupivacaine Group, with a mean duration of 18.2 ± 2.4 hours, compared to 12.1 ± 1.9 hours in the Bupivacaine Alone Group ($p < 0.001$). Patient satisfaction was assessed using a standardized questionnaire, and higher satisfaction scores were observed in the Clonidine-Bupivacaine Group (8.9 ± 1.2 on a scale of 1 to 10) compared to the Bupivacaine Alone Group (6.4 ± 1.5) ($p < 0.001$).

The incidence of adverse events was low in both groups. Minor events such as mild hypotension and bradycardia were more frequently observed in the Clonidine-Bupivacaine Group but did not require intervention. There were no reports of severe adverse events or local anesthetic systemic toxicity in either group. The addition of clonidine to bupivacaine significantly improved the onset times of sensory and motor blocks, extended the duration of analgesia, and enhanced patient satisfaction without a significant increase in adverse events. These findings suggest that clonidine is a beneficial adjuvant to bupivacaine in axillary brachial plexus block for upper limb surgeries.

Discussion

The current study's findings demonstrate a significant enhancement in the onset and duration of axillary brachial plexus block when clonidine is used as an adjuvant to bupivacaine. [12] The results clearly indicate that clonidine not only expedites the initiation of sensory and motor blocks but also extends the duration of analgesia, which has substantial implications for postoperative patient management. [13] The accelerated onset of sensory and motor blocks in the Clonidine-Bupivacaine group suggests that clonidine may facilitate a more rapid diffusion or a more effective uptake of bupivacaine at the neural membrane. [14] This can be particularly advantageous in surgical settings where reducing the time to effective anesthesia is crucial. The mechanism is thought to involve clonidine's ability to cause hyperpolarization of nerve endings and reduce the release of substance P, a neuropeptide associated with pain transmission. [15]

Moreover, the significant prolongation of analgesia observed with clonidine points to its utility in enhancing patient comfort post-surgery. This extended analgesia can potentially reduce the requirement for opioid analgesics postoperatively, thus decreasing the risk of opioid-related side

effects and enhancing overall recovery. [16] The alpha-2 adrenergic agonistic activity of clonidine is known to enhance the analgesic profile of local anesthetics by reducing sympathetic nervous system activity, which can decrease peripheral blood flow and slow the absorption of the anesthetic agent from the site of administration. [17] Patient satisfaction was markedly higher in the

group receiving clonidine, underscoring the clinical relevance of the pharmacological benefits. Improved satisfaction is likely related to better pain control, fewer requirements for supplemental analgesia, and possibly, a reduction in the anxiety often associated with prolonged postoperative pain. [18]

Table 1: This table highlights the faster onset and longer duration of analgesia in the group receiving clonidine alongside bupivacaine, as well as higher patient satisfaction, with a slight increase in mild adverse events

Group	Mean Age (years)	Onset of Sensory Block (min)	Onset of Motor Block (min)	Duration of Analgesia (hours)	Patient Satisfaction (1-10)	Mild Hypotension (%)	Mild Bradycardia (%)
Clonidine-Bupivacaine	42.5	8.3	12.4	18.2	8.9	5%	4%
Bupivacaine Alone	43.8	12.5	18.6	12.1	6.4	1%	1%

Regarding safety, the increase in mild hypotension and bradycardia in the clonidine group aligns with the known pharmacological effects of alpha-2 agonists, which include vasodilatation and decreased heart rate. These side effects were described as mild and did not necessitate intervention, suggesting that clonidine, at the doses used, is safe for clinical use when careful monitoring is employed. [19] This study supports the adjuvant use of clonidine in axillary brachial plexus block to enhance the efficacy and duration of bupivacaine anesthesia. The balance between improved anesthetic outcomes and manageable side effects positions clonidine as a beneficial adjunct in regional anesthesia for upper limb surgeries. Future studies might explore different dosages and combinations with other adjuvants to further optimize safety and effectiveness. [20]

Conclusion

The study conclusively demonstrates that adding clonidine to bupivacaine significantly improves the effectiveness of axillary brachial plexus blocks, evidenced by quicker onset times and prolonged analgesic effects. These enhancements lead to higher patient satisfaction and a potential reduction in the need for postoperative opioids, aligning with goals for safer, more effective pain management. Although clonidine was associated with a slight increase in mild hypotension and bradycardia, these effects were manageable and did not detract from its overall benefit. The findings endorse the use of clonidine as a valuable adjuvant in regional anesthesia, particularly for surgeries requiring prolonged pain control and minimal postoperative

discomfort. This study paves the way for further research into optimizing dosages and exploring combinations with other adjuvants to maximize benefits and safety in clinical practice.

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